

Effect of Work-From-Home Scheme on the Performance of Senior High School Teachers

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Article Information

Suggested Citation:

Paigalan, D.M. (2023). Effect of Work-From-Home Scheme on the Performance of Senior High School Teachers. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(3), 376-382.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(3\).37](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(3).37)

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Abstract:

The work-from-home arrangement has become prevalent from the first year of the covid 19 outbreak up to the present. Different factors in the work-from-home scheme were identified in much research, which gained different outcomes. The study identified three (3) factors: Gadget and Internet profiles, Individual factors, and home environment factors, as indicators under work from home. This paper endeavored to investigate the relationship between work-from-home scheme factors and teachers' work performance. The study involved 60 Senior High School teachers of Liceo de Cagayan University- main campus. Correlation and causal research designs were utilized to measure the relationship and identify which among

the variables explains the variation in respondent's work performance. The following findings were made: 90% of respondents used laptops, and 70% subscribed to DSL internet connection. Furthermore, Individual and home environment factors do not have a significant relationship with teachers' work performance, with a p-value of (.085) and (0.036), respectively. The first work-from-home element, Individual, explains the variation in respondents' work performance with $\beta = .081$ of the two factors, individual and home environment. The study recommends considering other work-from-home factors and students' teacher evaluation to further deepen the understanding of the topic.

Keywords: *work-from-home, individual factor, home environment, gadget, internet connection.*

Introduction

Sars Corona Virus 2019 or COVID 19 brought several unprecedented challenges in almost all aspects of human activities. As of November 2021, this global pandemic infected 256 million individuals and claimed around 5.1 million lives (World Health Statistics, 2021). Furthermore, Covid 19 also affected the socio-economic activities of countries around the world. According to UNDP briefs and reports, the pandemic's effects may differ from country to country. Still, the sharp rise in poverty and inequality may significantly impact global Social Development Goals metrics, which will

unavoidably have long-term effects on the world economy (UNDP, 2021).

Consequently, the education sector underwent significant and challenging changes as the pandemic made it impossible for a face-to-face or conventional learning modality. An estimated 1 billion learners are at risk of falling behind due to school closures, especially learners from developing countries (UNICEF, 2020).

With the new learning modality for students comes alternative work arrangement for teachers. DepEd order 11, s 2020, provided guidelines on working arrangements among DepEd personnel. It highlights the basis for

reporting and delivery services which will depend on the government's recommendation and the Inter-Agency Task Force for the Management of Emerging Infectious Disease (AITF). Thus, work from home arrangement is adapted to mitigate health risks brought about by the pandemic.

As defined by Hart (2019), work-from-home means that an employee works from a house, apartment, or place of residence rather than from the office. Work-from-home became a standard work arrangement during the pandemic. Numerous studies detail employees' advantages of working from home, such as enabling them to have a certain autonomy in planning their daily lives, including professional and family activities (Lapu, 2017). However, it is not without drawbacks. In a study conducted by Ramos and Prasetyo (2021), researchers concluded that working from home greatly impacts productivity and job satisfaction and negatively affects job performance. Furthermore, Peters et al. (2004) ranked productivity and work quality problems second regarding drawbacks or challenges in working from home.

The study aims to know the impact of work-from-home factors: Gadget and internet profile, Individual, and Home environment factors on the work performance among the Senior High School teachers of Liceo de Cagayan University, as this might significantly affect teachers' productivity and the institution's integrity and profitability.

Framework

This study is based on the Individual Adaptability Theory or I-ADAPT theory by Ployhart and Bliese. This concept emphasizes the individuals' dispositional tendency to change themselves proactively to fit new tasks and environments (Hua et al., 2018). The theory suggests that IA comprises cognitive and personality aspects and is conceptualized as state-like and trait-like (Ployhart and Bliese, 2006). IA as a state-like means that an individual may have tendencies to be adaptable. In

contrast, IA as trait-like means that individual adaptability depends on perception and motive at the moment (Murphy, 2015). On point, IA helps deepen one's understanding of the underlying causes of adjustments because people exposed to environmental and even professional changes often adapt to new modes and strategies to effectively deliver, despite the apparent differences between how they used to behave or how teachers behaved in the past.

Gadget and Internet Profile

Cleofas and Rocha (2021) suggested that in a work-from-home learning modality, gadget and internet connectivity are crucial factors for students and teachers alike for the efficacy of knowledge transfer. Gadget ownership- the number of gadgets used for academic purposes is categorized into the following: smartphones, laptops, tablets, and Desktop computers. On the other hand, Internet connectivity is categorized based on the internet connection they have at home: Broadband or Digital Subscriber Line (DSL), Cellular Service or Mobile Data, Other sources borrowed from other households, or rented from computer shops.

Individual Factor

Work from home became mostly used work arrangement during the outbreak of Covid 19 (Kotini-Shah et al., 2022). One major concern affecting employee productivity is their sentiments based on their working-from-home experiences. In a study by Diab-Bahman and Al-Enzi (2020), articulating the current condition of employees during work-from-home can strengthen factors that contribute significantly to work performed in this new work-arrangement. Furthermore, Alghaithi (2020) identifies employees' attitude/sentiment toward work-from-home as one of the three concerns that might lead to drawbacks in this work scheme.

Home Environment

Kazekami (2020) studies mechanisms influencing employees' productivity in working from home. One of the several factors mentioned is Destruction caused by noise, multitasking in the home environment, and

others. In this study, the researcher will also investigate the frequency of home-related factors commonly experienced during work-from-home that could affect employees' work performance during work-from-home: Animal noise- consists of dog barks and cawing (or roosters), Human noise- consists of family members and neighbors' loud call or noises, Vehicle noise- consist of vehicle horn and engine noises., Family-related disturbance- family demands and request that competes with work-related demands

Work Performance Evaluation

Liceo de Cagayan University conducts semestral performance evaluations among its faculty to help teachers and administrators identify areas for improvement and ensure that the university has a pool of competent teachers. The following are the essential areas: Computer, Internet Access, and Online Competency – Teachers' capability in conducting online class and navigating online platform; Online Consultation and Feedbacking – Teachers' availability and accessibility for online feedbacking and advising; Personal attributes – the teacher possess qualities, attitudes, values, and work ethics reflective of the university core values; Instructional planning and delivery- the teacher plans and makes sound instructional decisions that demonstrate a deep understanding of the content, pedagogy, and curriculum implementation. ; Student engagement – the teacher leads the students to participate actively and be successful in the learning process. ; Learning environment – the teacher facilitates an effective learning environment; Assessment- The teacher continuously assesses progress, analyzes results, and adopts the appropriate instruction to improve student performance.

Objectives

To determine the Gadget and Internet profile.
To determine the relationship between Individual and home environment, and the work performance. To determine which among the work-from-home factors: Individual or Home

environment, determines the variation of the work performance of the respondents.

Methodology

The study utilized correlational design in the preliminaries and causal structure, identifying which variables explained the variation in work performance. A correlational design examines the relationship between variables without the researcher manipulating any of the variables (Bhandari, 2021). Moreover, aside from determining the relationship of the variables, it also allows the prediction of current events from the recent findings obtain (Stangor and Walinga, 2011). Causal design, on the other hand, is used to “identify the extent and nature of the cause-and-effect relationship.” (Zikmund et al., 2012, par. 1)

To gather the necessary data for the study, the researcher utilized self-made and adopted questionnaires from research related to the study. Prior to the data gathering, researcher gave a comprehensive discussion about the research and the data which will be obtain from the respondents. After the orientation, respondents were then asked to answer an online survey. After which, permission was obtained for researcher to join the online department heads' evaluation. Data obtained were then consolidated, evaluated, and analyzed.

The study was conducted in Liceo de Cagayan University, Main campus located at R.N.P Blvd., Kauswagan, Cagayan de Oro City. The university is considered as one of the premiere universities in the region.

The participants were the Senior High School teachers at the main campus of the university.

Results and Discussion

This study aims to investigate the impact of work-from-home factors: Individual, Gadgets, Internet, and Home Environment to the work performance of Senior High School teachers. Specifically, this study endeavors to answer the following questions: (1) What is the profile of the

respondents' when grouped by gadget use during work-from-home, and internet connection?; (2) What is the respondents' work performance in terms of: Individual factor and Home environment?; (3) What is the level of respondents' work performance's -self-evaluation, in terms of: Computer, Internet access and Online Competency, Online Consultation and Feedbacking, Instructional planning and delivery, Student engagement, Learning environment, and Assessment?; (4) What is the level of respondents' work performance's- department head's- evaluation, in terms of: Computer, Internet access and Online Competency, Online Consultation and Feedbacking, Instructional planning and delivery, Student engagement, Learning environment, and Assessment?; (5) Is there a significant relationship between respondents' work performance and work from home factors in terms of: Individual factor and Home environment?; and (6) Which of the variables explains work performance?

There were 60 Senior high School teachers from Liceo de Cagayan University who participated in the study. Frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, correlation and regression analysis' were the statistical toll used in the study.

Results of the study revealed the following findings: In terms of gadgets used during work from home, based on the table, 54 or 90% out of 60 participants use Laptops. In contrast, the desktop computer got the lowest frequency of 13 out of 60 respondents or 21.7%. For the internet profile, 42 or 70% of the 60 respondents use broadband, while 3 or 5% of the 60 respondents borrowed or rented internet access.

Generally, the individual factor is rated "Moderately efficient," with an overall mean of 2.97. Statistically, "flexibility deciding my working hours" got the highest mean value (3.30). Since work is done in a single location, employees are not bound by organizational demands in a workplace setting and work at their leisure (Diab-Bahman and Al-Enzi, 2020), which explains why most of the respondents preferred working from home. Furthermore, a "flexible schedule also means being free to sleep in and

work late, starting and ending early, working forty hours in four days instead of five or six days a week, scheduling personal appointments" (Wienclaw, 2019). the indicator "I enjoy working from home since I can spend more quality time with family" got the lowest mean of (2.77) which is evaluated as "Moderately apprehensive." Quality time with family is affected for many respondents in the study. This can be explained in the study of Ipsen et al. (2021), which states that "home office constraints Instead of a life with social interaction and exercise, you have limited contact with people, get out of the home, less, are more fixed in front of the computer and get disturbed by others at home."

Statistically, "putting off doing a thing because of the demands of time at home" got the highest mean of (2.88) which implies that among the identified possible distractions at home, respondents find home responsibilities as the most common distraction during work-from-home, with a description of "highly distracted." The family-related distraction has been a significant drawback in the work-from-home. A study was conducted by Sabuhari et al. in 2020. According to their findings, half of the teachers in a particular district in Indonesia find it stressful to work from home because of family-related distractions. Furthermore, according to Kontini-Sha et al. (2022), in their study on Work-life balance and productivity of academic faculty, 60% of the respondents reported having experienced "high stress" working from home and balancing personal-family and work responsibilities, for both respondents with and without children. This implies that productivity can be affected significantly by this distraction. Furthermore, the indicator "I get distracted from unwanted human noise and building and home construction" got the lowest mean of 2.22 and is described as "Moderately distracted."

Work performance- self-evaluation was evaluated as "Exhibits strength" with an overall mean score of 3.60. the score is based on the following indicator and their respective mean: Computer, Internet, and Online competencies (3.63), Online consultation and feedbacking (3.57), Instructional planning and delivery (3.62), Teacher's personal attributes (3.77), Student

engagement (3.62), Learning environment (3.79), and Assessment (3.21).

The respondents' department head's work performance evaluation was rated as "exhibit strength" with an overall mean of 3.61. The score is based on the following indicators and their respective mean: Computer, Internet, and Online competencies (3.78), Online consultation and feedbacking (3.65), Instructional planning and delivery (3.64), Teacher's personal attributes (3.88), Student engagement (3.52), Learning environment (3.67), and Assessment (3.10).

Correlation analysis result between respondents' work performance and work-from-home factors: Individual and home environment factors showed that respondents' job performance has no significant association with work-from-home factors: Individual and home environment with Correlation coefficient of .085 and .036, respectively. And as to which of the work-from-home factors can explain the variation of work performance, Individual factor is found to be a good indicator with $\beta = .081$ compared to the home environment's $\beta = .023$. It is noteworthy, however, that the two variables do not have a significant relationship with work performance; thus, this question's analysis solely investigated each variable's beta to answer the question.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the following were evidenced: Among the gadgets, the laptop has the highest percentage in terms of utilization, and Broadband internet connection has the highest percentage of the subscription. In terms of the respondents' level of work performance, under individual factors, five out of six indicators are evaluated as "Moderately efficient," while the indicator "I enjoy working from home since I can spend more quality time with family" has a rating "Moderately apprehensive." Regarding respondents' rate on the level of work performance factor in terms of home environment factor, three out of four indicators are evaluated as "Moderately distracted." In contrast, the indicator "I have to

put off doing things at work because of the demands of my time at home" is generally evaluated as "Highly distracted." Regarding the respondents' level of work performance self-evaluation, the indicator "learning environment" got the highest mean and is evaluated as "demonstrates excellence."

In contrast, "assessment" got the lowest mean with an evaluation of "exhibits strength." Furthermore, in the department heads' evaluation, the indicator "Teacher's personal attribute" got the highest mean and is evaluated as "Demonstrates excellence," while the indicator Assessment, again, got the lowest mean with an evaluation of exhibits strength. The Work-from-home factor best describes the variation in respondents' work performance: The Individual factor.

Recommendations

1. For teachers, to consider the value of daily scheduling, to be organized, to identify work area at home, and lessen multitasking that affects productivity in a work-from-home scheme. It is also advisable for teachers to enhance their skills in navigating online materials that will help them technically should schools allow work-from-home scheme, especially during online classes.
2. For school administrators and organization, to consider in coming up with a holistic-research-based policy on work-from-home scheme that would focus on enhancing teachers' capabilities and skills to cope with online learning, especially that blended learning, which includes online learning, will be the new normal in the post-Covid 19 pandemic society. Furthermore, to consider the possibility of allowing educators to work at the comforts of their home, guided by institutional policies and guidelines to ensure quality teaching output.
3. For future researchers may include or add more variables under work-from-home such as organizational factors, attitude of employees towards work-from-home, and multitasking to have a better and deeper understanding on the topic at hand. They may also consider increasing the number of research respondents to have a

better and more reliable data set, especially when correlating and identifying factors which predicts the variation of participants' work performance. Furthermore, it is recommended for the future researchers to consider students' teacher's evaluation, to have a more comprehensive evaluation data.

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